

CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED EPOXY COMPOSITES WITH VARIABLE STIFFNESS FOR USE IN MORPHING AEROSTRUCTURES

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1 Introduction

Morphing aerostructures have the potential to improve the performance of aircraft through reductions in weight and drag [1] and to have lower maintenance requirements than wings with conventional control surfaces. One configuration of a morphing wing requires a stiff skin material that can transfer aerodynamic loads but that can also be deformed on demand with acceptable actuation forces [2, 3]. A previous study has shown that a fibre reinforced elastomer can provide a suitable balance of load carrying ability and flexibility for the morphing skin of a model aircraft wing [4]. Carbon fibre composites with controllable flexural stiffness have recently been devised that may provide the means to avoid compromising on the properties of a morphing wing skin [5, 6]. (Such materials may also have applications in deployable and collapsible structures.) This paper summarises the results of an experimental programme investigating the stiffness characteristics of various configurations of this controllable stiffness composite, examines the effectiveness of simple beam theory to predict the observed behaviour, and describes current trials in which integrated heating (to achieve the stiffness control) and integrated actuation are investigated.

2 Concept

Controllable stiffness has been achieved by introducing thermoplastic polymer interleaf layers in a laminated carbon fibre reinforced polymer (cfrp) composite. The thermoplastic

polymer is chosen so that its glass transition temperature (T_g) is less than that of the cfrp plies. The simplest configuration, consisting of two cfrp plies separated by a single interleaf layer, is shown in Fig. 1. When bent at room temperature the shear stiffness of the interleaf material is sufficient to ensure that the two cfrp plies act as an integral structural element. When the composite is heated to a temperature above the T_g of the thermoplastic (but below that of the cfrp) the cfrp plies can slide relative to each other and so the flexural stiffness of the laminate is significantly reduced.

3 Experimental investigation of flexural stiffness

3.1 Specimen and test details

A control laminate and three interleaved composite laminates (A, B & C) were manufactured using plies of unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced epoxy (HexPly, 914C-TS-5-34%, Hexcel, nominal ply thickness = 0.126 mm, $T_g = 175$ °C) and interleaf layers of polystyrene ($T_g = 100$ °C). See Table 1 for the layup details. From these laminates flexural test specimens were prepared with a width of 10 mm and length of 80 mm and with the 0° direction of the cfrp plies aligned with the longitudinal direction of the specimen.

An additional special laminate, termed 'constrained' in Table 1, was prepared in which the interleaf layers only existed in the central 28 mm of a smaller flexure specimen (10 mm wide, 40 mm long) and were substituted with composite plies in the outer portions (see Fig. 2).

In this way the composite plies of the specimen were constrained from relative sliding at the ends of the flexure specimen.

Three point bending tests were performed in accordance with ASTM D7264 [7] at room temperature and at 120°C. The test fixture had loading and support bars of 6mm diameter and the supports were adjusted to achieve a span to thickness ratio of 32 in all the tests. The tests were conducted at a cross-head displacement speed of 1 mm / min on an Instron 4505 test machine fitted with a 1 kN load cell. For the first series of tests, specimens were loaded to a maximum deflection of 1 mm at room temperature and then unloaded. The tests were then repeated at 120°C in an environmental chamber and then again at room temperature.

3.2 Flexural test results

A typical plot of load against displacement measured in the three-point flexure test on composite B is shown in Fig. 3. A large loss in stiffness is evident when the specimen is tested at 120°C and the second room temperature test shows that the stiffness is fully recovered on cooling.

The flexural modulus, E_f , of the specimens was calculated using equation 1, where L is support span, w is beam width, h is beam thickness and m is the gradient of the load - displacement curve. To calculate the average flexural modulus of the composites, five specimens of each sample were tested.

$$E_f = \frac{L^3 m}{4wh^3} \quad (1)$$

The resulting flexural moduli are given in Table 2.

It can be seen that when the specimens are heated to 120 °C (i.e. above the T_g of the polystyrene) the flexural modulus of the composite was greatly reduced. At this temperature the polystyrene softened and allowed the reinforced plies to slide relative to each other (see Fig. 4), permitting large deflections without any damage to the composite. The composite could be cooled in its deformed shape and that shape would be maintained. On

reheating, the unloaded specimens would return to their original straight shape and when retested at room temperature the original flexural modulus was measured.

4 Prediction by simple beam theory

Beam theory was used to predict the flexural stiffness behaviour of the interleaved composite specimens of laminates A, B and C at room temperature and 120 °C.

At room temperature, it is assumed that plane sections originally normal to the axis of the beam, remain plane and normal after bending and so the effective flexural modulus, E_f^* , can be determined for a symmetric laminate as follows. First the reduced second moment of area, I_r , is calculated using equation 2.

$$I_r = w \sum_{\substack{\text{all cfrp} \\ \text{plies}}} \left(\frac{t_i^3}{12} + t_i y_i'^2 \right) \quad (2)$$

in which, as indicated in Fig. 5, t_i is the thickness of a cfrp ply, y_i' is the y coordinate of the mid-plane of the ply measured from the mid-plane of the laminate and w is the width of the beam cross-section. The calculation of I_r ignores the contribution of the polystyrene layers because the elastic modulus of this material is very small compared to that of the cfrp. The product of I_r and E_c , the longitudinal elastic modulus of the cfrp plies, is then equated to $E_f^* I$ in which E_f^* is the effective flexural modulus and I is the second moment of area of the full beam section. (Using the notation of Fig. 5, $I = wh^3/12$.) E_f^* is therefore given by equation 3.

$$E_f^* = \frac{E_c I_r}{I} \quad (3)$$

This value of E_f^* is the predicted value of the room temperature flexural modulus of the composite and can be compared to the value determined in the flexural test.

At 120 °C, each of the cfrp blocks (formed by one or more adjoining cfrp plies separated from other cfrp blocks by the polystyrene layers) is assumed to act independently and to be able to slide freely relative to the adjacent blocks. The total flexural

stiffness can therefore be determined from E_c multiplied by the sum of the second moment of area values ($\sum I_b$) where I_b is the second moment of area of each block about its own mid plane. (So, for example, I_b for the block formed by the cfrp plies j , k and l in Fig. 5 is $w(t_j+t_k+t_l)^3/12$.) The product $E_c\sum I_b$ can again be equated to E_f^*I and so the predicted value of E_f^* at high temperature is given by equation 4.

$$E_f^* = \frac{E_c \sum_{\text{blocks}} \text{all cfrp } I_b}{I} \quad (4)$$

For the constrained laminate specimen at room temperature, equation 3 gives the predicted flexural modulus. At 120°C the individual cfrp blocks are again assumed to be free to slide relative to each other but these blocks are now constrained at each support by the solid cfrp end sections. At each of these positions it is assumed that the plane section, originally normal to the beam axis before bending, will remain plane and normal after bending. To determine a theoretical value for the effective flexural modulus of the constrained specimen at high temperature, the 3-point bend test is considered to be the superposition of two configurations as shown in Fig. 6. In case I the beam is treated as fixed-ended (enforcing zero rotation at the supports). The individual cfrp blocks of the beam section are assumed to act as independent beams, all deflecting the same amount at the load point. The flexural stiffness of the beam is therefore given as $E_c\sum I_b$ and the central deflection is given by equation 5.

$$\delta_I = \frac{PL^3}{192E_c \sum_{\text{blocks}} \text{all cfrp } I_b} \quad (5)$$

where L is the length of the beam.

In load case I there will be reaction moments M_R (equal to $PL/8$) which do not exist in the real 3-point bend test. In load case II (Fig. 6) the simply supported beam is subjected to moments M_R applied in the opposite direction to those generated in load case I. (In this way the superposition of load cases I and II is equivalent

to the original 3-point bend test.) When subjected to M_R the beam will deform with a constant curvature and because of constraints at the support then all plane sections, normal to the axis of the beam will remain so after bending. The flexural stiffness of the beam for this load case is therefore given by the room temperature expression E_cI_r and the central deflection, δ_{II} , is given by equation 6.

$$\delta_{II} = \frac{PL^3}{64E_cI_r} \quad (6)$$

By equating the expression for the total deflection ($\delta_I + \delta_{II}$) to the equation for the central deflection of an homogenous beam subjected to 3-point bending ($PL^3/48E_f^*I$), equation 7 can be derived for the effective modulus of the constrained beam specimen at high temperature

$$E_f^* = \frac{4E_cI_r \sum_{\text{blocks}} \text{all cfrp } I_b}{I \left(I_r + 3 \sum_{\text{blocks}} \text{all cfrp } I_b \right)} \quad (7)$$

The flexural moduli, predicted using equations 3, 4 and 7, are presented in Table 3.

It can be seen that the simple beam theory yields values for the percentage loss in flexural modulus which are in good agreement with the experimentally observed values. The theory over-predicts the room temperature flexural moduli (presumably because the theory does not include shear distortion of the polystyrene layers). At 120 °C the theoretical predictions are lower than the measured values and this is because theory completely disregards the residual shear stiffness of the softened thermoplastic layers.

5 Development of a cantilever beam with integrated actuation and heating

5.1 Manufacture and experimental evaluation

Trials have been conducted to demonstrate the potential benefits of using a controllable stiffness composite in a morphing device. A simple cantilever beam consisting of two plies of unidirectional cfrp separated by one layer of polystyrene has been manufactured with a free

length of 85 mm and a width of 20 mm. The beam has a thin Kapton film encapsulated heater (manufactured by Omega Engineering – see Fig. 7) bonded to the lower surface so as to raise the temperature up to 120°C as required for significant flexural stiffness loss. Bonded to the upper surface is a macro fibre composite (MFC) actuator (by Smart Material Corp under licence from NASA). The layup details and key properties of the heater and actuators are given in Table 4.

The tip deflection was measured for actuator voltages up to 400V at room temperature and when heated to almost 120 °C. As shown in Fig. 9 the response was linear in both cases and the measured maximum tip deflections are recorded in Table 5. For this thin laminate the deflection was increased by 118% when the flexural stiffness of the composite was reduced by heating.

5.2 Prediction of actuated behaviour

A beam-based theoretical approach can be used to predict the response of the actuator/heater/composite assembly (see Fig. 10 for the cross-section and notation to be used). For the room temperature case it is again assumed that the laminate acts as an integral structural element (i.e. plane sections, originally normal to the axis of the beam, remain plane and normal after bending). It is simpler if the origin of the y-axis is chosen to be the elastic centroid and the position of this can be determined using equation 8.

$$\bar{y}_e = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N E_i t_i \bar{y}'_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N E_i t_i} \quad (8)$$

in which \bar{y}'_i is the \bar{y} coordinate of the mid-plane of lamina i , t_i & E_i are the thickness and longitudinal Young's modulus of lamina i , and N is the number of laminae in the full assembly. The origin of \bar{y} can be chosen for convenience; in Fig. 10 it is shown at the bottom edge of the beam cross-section.

The longitudinal direct stress in ply i is given by equation 9.

$$\sigma|_{\text{for ply } i} = E_i \left(\varepsilon_0 + \frac{y}{R} - \gamma_i \Delta v \right) \quad (9)$$

where ε_0 is the longitudinal direct strain at the elastic centroid, $1/R$ is the curvature of the beam axis, γ_i is the longitudinal voltage expansion coefficient, Δv is the applied voltage and y (measured from the elastic centroid) falls within lamina i . Note that γ_i will only be non-zero for the actuator ply.

These direct stresses, multiplied by y , can then be integrated over the height of the beam to give the moment resultant per unit width of the beam. Noting that there is no externally applied moment then equation 10 results.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\Delta v}{2} \sum_{i=1}^N E_i \gamma_i (y_i^2 - y_{i-1}^2) \\ = \frac{1}{3R} \sum_{i=1}^N E_i (y_i^3 - y_{i-1}^3) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where y_i is the y coordinate of the interface between the i^{th} ply and the $(i+1)^{\text{th}}$ ply. The left hand side only has a non-zero γ_i for the actuator ply and so the resulting curvature is given by equation 11.

$$\frac{1}{R} = \frac{\frac{\Delta v}{2} \{E_i \gamma_i (y_i^2 - y_{i-1}^2)\}_{\text{actuator ply only}}}{\frac{1}{3} \sum_{i=1}^N E_i (y_i^3 - y_{i-1}^3)} \quad (11)$$

The term on the denominator is the weighted second moment of area of the beam section about an axis (horizontal in Fig. 10) passing through the elastic centroid and can be written as $\sum_{i=1}^N E_i I_i$ where I_i is the second moment of area of ply i about the elastic centroid. The numerator can be considered as the voltage-induced moment per unit width, M_v , and so equation 11 can be rewritten as equation 12.

$$\frac{1}{R} = \frac{M_v}{\sum_{i=1}^N E_i I_i} \quad (12)$$

Finally, the tip deflection, δ , at room temperature is given by equation 13.

$$\delta = \frac{1}{R} \frac{L^2}{2} \quad (13)$$

When the heater is switched on and the specimen temperature approaches 120°C, the beam section can be considered to consist of two beams: the

upper beam consisting of the actuator and a cfrp ply and the lower one consisting of a cfrp ply and the heater. Assuming that the upper and lower beams deflect with the same curvature and that this is constant along the beam, then the previous room temperature analysis can be modified to show that the curvature is now given by equation 14.

$$\frac{1}{R} = \frac{\frac{\Delta v}{2} \{E_i \gamma_i (y_i^{U^2} - y_{i-1}^{U^2})\}_{\text{actuator ply only}}}{\frac{1}{3} \sum_{\text{upper beam plies}} E_i (y_i^{U^3} - y_{i-1}^{U^3}) + \frac{1}{3} \sum_{\text{lower beam plies}} E_i (y_i^{L^3} - y_{i-1}^{L^3})}$$

$$= \frac{M_v^U}{\sum_{\text{upper beam plies}} E_i I_i^U + \sum_{\text{lower beam plies}} E_i I_i^L} \quad (14)$$

where y^U and y^L are the y coordinates with their origin at the elastic centroid of the upper beam and the lower beam respectively, I^U and I^L are the second moments of area calculated about the elastic centroidal axes of the upper and lower beams respectively, and M_v^U is the voltage-induced moment about the elastic centroidal axis of the upper beam.

This can be readily extended to a thicker composite beam which could degenerate into more than two sub-beams. The tip deflection is agiven by inserting the curvature from equation 14 into equation 13.

Using the data of Table 4, the predicted displacements for an actuator voltage of 400V have been calculated using equations 12-14 and are given in Table 5. It can be seen that there is reasonable agreement between the experimental and predicted values. The potential sources of discrepancies are being investigated.

6 Conclusions

This paper has shown that stiffness control is possible with thermoplastic interleaved composites. The experimentally observed loss in flexural stiffness is predicted well with simple beam theory. Trials have been conducted to

evaluate the performance of this controllable stiffness composite with surface-mounted heating and actuation. For the specimen used here, the tests show that the displacement is increased by over 100% when the flexural stiffness is reduced by heating and the beam-based analysis predicts this increase reasonably well.

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Fig. 1. Concept of interleaved composite with controllable stiffness.

Fig. 2 Geometry of constrained flexural specimen

Fig. 3. Typical load-displacement plots at room and elevated temps for composite B (heated using environmental chamber)

Fig. 5 Notation for beam cross-section geometry

Fig. 4. Relative deformation of plies due to shear strain in polystyrene at elevated temperature

Fig. 6. a) Load case I: point load with built-in ends (cfrp blocks acting as separate structural elements) b) Load case II: simply supported beam with negative end moments from case I (laminate acting as an integral structural element) c) Combined load case (equivalent to 3-point flexure test on constrained laminate)

Fig. 7. Kapton film heater

Fig. 10. Cross-section of actuated cantilever specimen

Fig. 8. Actuation using MFC actuator

Laminate	Layup*
Control	$[0^{\circ}_{16}]$
A	$[(0^{\circ}/P^{109})_4/0^{\circ}/(P^{109}/0^{\circ})_4]$
B	$[0^{\circ}_3/P^{196}/0^{\circ}_3/P^{196}/0^{\circ}_3/P^{196}/0^{\circ}_3]$
C	$[0^{\circ}_4/P^{68}/0^{\circ}_4/P^{68}/0^{\circ}_4/P^{68}/0^{\circ}_4]$
Constrained	$[0^{\circ}/P^{109}/0^{\circ}/P^{109}/0^{\circ}/P^{109}/0^{\circ}]$

* 0° indicates a cfrp ply, P^t indicates a polystyrene layer of thickness $t \mu\text{m}$

Table 1. Specimen Laminate details

Fig.9. Cantilever tip deflection vs. actuator input voltage at room temperature and elevated temperature.

Laminate	Flexural Modulus* (GPa)		% loss
	RT	120 °C	
Control	118 (3)	112 (2)	5.1
A	65 (3)	1 (0.2)	98.5
B	90 (1)	4 (1)	95.5
C	107 (7)	7 (0.02)	94.1
Constrained	69 (6)	7 (0.4)	89.9

* mean (standard deviation) of modulus are shown

Table 2. Measured flexural moduli

Laminate	E _f * (GPa)		% loss
	RT	120 °C	
Composite A	73.5	0.3	99.6
Composite B	98.0	2.8	97.2
Composite C	112.2	5.5	95.1
Constrained	87.5	6.2	92.9

Table 3. Predicted flexural moduli

Layer No.	Material	Thickness (mm)	E (GPa)	Voltage expansion coeff (/V)
1	actuator	0.3	30.3	0.75e-6
2	cfrp	0.126	118	-
3	polystyrene	0.13	2.5	-
4	cfrp	0.126	118	-
5	heater	0.2	2.5	-

Table 4. Cantilever specimen data

Source	Deflection, δ (mm)		% increase
	RT	120 °C	
Experiment	1.6	3.5	118
Predicted	1.8	3.4	91

Table 5. Experimentally measured and predicted tip deflections of actuated cantilever specimen at 400V

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